

INFLUENCE OF HEAT TREATMENT ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH IN AL7075 ALLOY

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Abstract:

The fatigue crack growth threshold defines the stress intensity level, ΔK , below which a crack will not propagate. Recent research has shown some of the threshold data generated based on ISO and ASTM testing standards has some limitations, influencing the data in unforeseen ways. One of these limitations refers to the steady-state condition of threshold value. In the present study in view of the limitation mentioned an attempt has been made to determine the fatigue threshold value by regression analysis. In the present study Al7075 alloy is subjected to heat treatment such as annealing and cryogenic treatment and tested for fatigue crack growth (FCG) as per ASTM E-647 standards. Servohydraulic controlled fatigue crack growth testing machine was used for load ratio of 0.1 and frequency of 30Hz at constant amplitude cycle. The experimental results show an improvement in crack resistance for cryotreated Al7075 alloy. Annealed Al7075 showed improved stiffness compared to cryo-treated specimen. Microstructure analysis revealed changes in microstructure of specimens, which influence the mechanical characteristics of the material.

Key Words: ISO, ASTM, cryogenic treatment, annealing, fatigue crack growth (FCG).

Introduction:

Fatigue and impact loads are considered very seriously in the design of components especially in aircrafts, ships, and thermal power plants. The study of crack growth and propagation is very important in such components subjected to fatigue and impact loads. Aluminium alloys are of great importance when relatively high strength, good corrosion resistance and high toughness are required in conjunction

with good formability and weld ability. Aluminum alloy, Al 7075 with Mg and Zn as alloying elements has many applications on aircraft fittings, marine applications, gears and shafts, hydraulic valves, nuts, pistons, worm gears, couplings and fastening devices .The fatigue crack growth study involves the prediction of the fatigue life, fracture toughness, crack growth rate and stress intensity range of a structure or machine component subjected to a given stress–time history. Due to the increasing use of Al 7075 alloy components in automotive and aerospace applications that involve cyclic loading, fatigue and fatigue crack growth characteristics of Al 7075 are of great interest.

In the present investigation Al 7075 is selected for the study of crack growth and propagation under fatigue loading. Compact test (CT) specimens were prepared as per ASTM E-647 standards for fatigue crack growth tests. Specimens were subjected to processes of annealing, cryotreatment and a combination of annealing and cryo treatment. The results obtained from the tests were analyzed with the help of microstructures.

Examination of the mechanism of fatigue-crack propagation with particular emphasis on the similarities and differences between cyclic crack growth in ductile materials such as metals, and corresponding behaviour in brittle materials was examined by R.O. Ritchie [5].This was achieved by considering the process of fatigue crack growth as a mutual competition between intrinsic mechanisms of crack advance ahead of the crack tip, which promote crack growth, and extrinsic mechanisms of crack –tip shielding behind the tip, which impede it. Influence of heat treatment on fatigue crack growth in heat treated Al-8089 alloy was studied [16].From the experimental data it was observed that heat treated alloy possessed acceptable level of crack resistance ,compared to other high strength aluminium alloys.

The Fatigue Rate Curve:

It is a crack growth rate (da/dN) versus stress intensity range (ΔK) curve as shown in Fig.1. The curve is often divided into three regions; Region I, Region II and Region III. In region I the early development of the fatigue crack represented, and the growth rate is in the order 10⁻⁶mm/cycle or below. This region is very sensitive to micro structure features like grain size, the means stress of the applied load, the environment and the operating temperature. The most important feature in this region is the FCG threshold, ΔK_{th}. This is the limit for the propagation of fatigue cracks start. For SIF ranges below the ΔK_{th} crack growth will usually not occur .Region II is the intermediate zone for growth rates in the order of 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻³mm/cycle. In this region the crack growth is stable, the data is following a power equation and the plastic zone in front of the crack tip is large compared to the mean grain size. The pari’s equation for region II of the curve is given by

$$da/dN=CΔK^m \quad \text{-----1}$$

Where C and m are material parameters, ΔK is stress intensity range.

Since the data is following a power equation, the fit will be linear on a log-log plot and the use of LEFM concepts are applicable. For region II the mean stress has the highest influence on the results, but the influence is small compared with region I.

Fig. 1: Fatigue crack growth rate curve

The last region, region III, starts where the curve again become steep, and is usually in the order 10^{-3} mm/cycle and above. This is high crack growth rates caused by the rapid unstable growth prior to final failure. The curve approaches in this region an asymptote corresponding to the fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , for the material. The influence of nonlinear properties cannot be ignored in this region due the present of large scale yielding. This result in that LEFM cannot be used for the data in this region and nonlinear fracture mechanics should be applied instead. FCG analysis for this region is therefore very complex and as the FCG rates are high and little fatigue life involved. This result often in that analysis for this region is ignored.

Material selection:

Al 7075 was selected for the study as this material finds applications in aircraft, marine and automobile industries. The chemical composition of Al 7075 alloy is shown in table I.

TABLE I: Chemical composition of Al 7075

Material	Aluminum (Al)	Copper (Cu)	Magnesium (Mg)	Zinc (Zn)	Manganese(Mn),Silicon (Si),Chromium(Cr)
Weight %	90.1 %	1.4%	2.3%	5.8%	0.4 %

Specimen Preparation:

Fatigue crack growth tests characterize the rate at which pre-existing cracks in metals, ceramics, composites and other materials propagate as a function of a cyclic driving force, most commonly the range of applied stress intensity. Fatigue crack growth tests generate data that can be used as a basis for setting inspection intervals in components designed for damage tolerance. Specimens as per ASTM E-647[10] were prepared with 12.5 mm thickness as shown in fig.2.

Fig.2: specifications of FCG test specimen as per ASTM E 647 standards

Heat treatment and cryogenic treatment of specimens:

The specimens of FCG tests were subjected to annealing, cryogenic treatment and the combination of annealing followed by cryogenic treatment. Annealing was carried out at 450° C for one hour followed by cooling in the furnace for 24 hours. Cryogenic treatment was carried at -178° C for 24 hours with 4 hours of cool down and 9 hours of warming up time in a specially developed cryotreatment unit using liquid nitrogen as the coolant. The setup used is as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3 photograph of the cryotreatment unit

Fatigue crack growth Test:

Fatigue crack growth tests were carried out using servo hydraulic controlled fatigue crack growth testing machine of 25 KN capacity as per ASTM E-647 standards. FCG tests were carried out at a loading frequency of 30 Hz, load ratio of 0.1 for maximum load of 2 KN, minimum load of 0.2 KN with Constant amplitude cycle. Fig. 4 shows the FCG test setup.

Fig.4: specimen loaded on the servo hydraulic controlled fatigue crack growth testing system.

Results and Discussions:

Tests with a constant load ratio, $R = 0.1$ were performed at room temperature in accordance with ASTM E647 standard using compact tension specimens, to determine the threshold value. The test systems were calibrated to meet or exceed the requirements of ASTM E647. The displacement gages, strain gages and signal conditioners were calibrated to assure linearity in the operating regime. All testing was conducted under K-control with all crack length measurements verified using travelling microscope of the machine. The visual measurements were used to correct the compliance-based crack length values prior to data reporting per ASTM E647.

Fig.5: da/dN vs ΔK for untreated Al 7075 alloy

Fig.6: da/dN vs ΔK for cryo treated Al 7075 alloy

Fig.7: da/dN vs ΔK for annealed Al 7075 alloy

Fig.8: da/dN vs ΔK for annealed+Cryo treated Al 7075 alloy

Figures 5,6,7 and 8 shows variation of crack growth rate with stress intensity range for various heat treated Al7075. In all the graphs it is observed that crack growth rate increases linearly with the increase in stress intensity range in the region II of fatigue crack growth curve. Fatigue threshold and fracture toughness values for heat treated Al 7075 are obtained from figures 5, 6, 7 and 8 using best curve fitting the values are tabulated in the table II. Threshold value for cryotreated specimen is maximum among the heat treated specimens. Whereas its value is minimum for the combination of annealed and cryotreated specimens

Figure 9 is a comparison of number of cycles to failure of the specimen under different heat treated conditions. From the graph it is clear that number of cycles to failure is maximum for cryotreated Al 7075 as it becomes ductile due to uniform grain structure therefore crack moves slowly, resulting in improved crack resistance. As brittleness of the alloy is increased after heat treatment the crack resistance decreased resulting in poor crack resistance to fatigue cycles. It is also observed that there is further reduction in crack resistance for an alloy subjected to the combination of annealing and cryogenic treatment. It is mainly due to decreased ductility of the material, hence crack propagates easily.

Table II: Fatigue threshold and fracture toughness values for heat treated Al7075

Material	Regression coefficient R ²	Threshold (MPa√m) K _{th}	Fracture Toughness(MPa√m) K _c
Untreated Al 7075 alloy	0.909	9.4719	16.62
Cryotreated Al 7075 alloy	0.921	10.39	16.69
annealed Al 7075 alloy	0.909	9.181	14.43
Combination of annealed and cryotreated Al 7075 alloy	0.907	9.028	14.36

Fig.9: Number of cycles to failure under various heat treatment conditions

Microstructure of Al-2024 alloy:

Microstructure and material flow have a significant influence on the mechanical properties and surface quality [9]. Microstructure analysis includes measurement of grain size, determination of inclusions, phase determination and density of dislocations. In the present investigation microstructure of Al 7075 alloy was obtained using inverted metallurgical microscope for different heat treatment conditions at 200X and 500X magnifications. The salient features of the analysis of the specimens are discussed below.

Fig.10: Microstructure of untreated Al 7075 alloy at 500X **Fig.11:** Microstructure of cryo treated Al 7075 alloy at 500X

Fig.12: Microstructure of Heat Treated Al 7075 alloy at 500X

Fig.13: Microstructure of Combination of Heat Treated and Cryotreated Al 7075 alloy at 500X

Cryotreated Al 7075 shows the change in orientation of the grain structure compared to untreated Al 7075. Due to uniform grain structure material possess improved fatigue life. Figure 11 shows the microstructure of cryotreated Al 2024 alloy at 500X. Figure 12 shows the microstructure of annealed Al 7075. It is observed that refined grain structure is obtained in the specimen subjected to annealing. As the annealing increases the brittleness of the material resulting in less energy absorbing capacity under fatigue load hence possesses poor fatigue life. The combination of annealing and the cryotreatment results in the reorientation of grains structure and uniform distribution of the constituents as shown in figure 13.

Conclusions:

Specimens of Al 7075 were prepared as per ASTM E-647 standard specifications and were subjected heat treatment, cryogenic treatment and the combination of heat treatment and cryogenic treatment. Fatigue crack growth test reveals improved crack resistance in cryo treated sample as compared to other heat treated samples hence it possessed higher values of fatigue threshold and fracture toughness and withstood maximum number of cycles among the samples. Heat treated sample possessed poor fatigue crack resistance due to increased brittleness hence the threshold and fracture toughness values are smaller compared to other heat treated samples. Effect of cryo treatment on the heat treated sample further increased brittleness which results poor threshold and fracture toughness.

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International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research, Volume 1, Issue 4, Aug-2014, pp 75-82

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